

***Pseudomonas* species causing rice sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (GID)**

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Four *Pseudomonas* spp. cause ShR and GID of rice. *P. glumae* and *P. avenae* primarily cause spikelet sterility and GID, and only slightly affect the sheath at the collar. *P. fuscovaginae* and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* cause severe ShR as well as sterility and GID. GID symptoms caused by the different pathogenic species are virtually indistinguishable in winnowed grain samples. ShR symptoms of *P. fuscovaginae* and *P. syringae* also are similar.

We studied 153 isolates from 26 countries under quarantine conditions, to identify characteristics that clearly differentiate the species. The tests performed were pathogenicity on rice seedlings; Gram stain; indole test; fluorescent pigment production; oxidase; arginine dihydrolase; lecithinase; catalase; ripase; nitrate and 2-ketogluconate reduction; utilization of 30 carbohydrates for growth; hydrolysis of casein, aesculin, starch; gelatin liquefaction; acetoin, levan and urease production; pectin gel pitting, H₂S from TS1; acid and gas production from lactose, E-methyl glucoside, sucrose and rhamnose, potato soft rot; NaCl tolerance (5%); growth on sorbitol neutral red agar medium (used to isolate *P. avenae*) = SNR, S.P.G. medium, citrate agar, acetate agar, blood agar; methyl red reaction; hypersensitivity of tobacco; and growth at 4, 37, and 41°C. Responses of the species are presented in the table.

While the species can be readily differentiated by these tests, considerable care should be taken to determine that isolates are pathogenic on rice and that they are pure. This is particularly important for the fluorescent species.

Two nonpathogenic fluorescent species commonly isolated from rice grain, *P. putida* and *P. fluorescens*, give

Character differentiation of isolates of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, *P. avenae*, *P. glumae*, and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola*.^a

Characteristic	Fluorescent		Nonfluorescent	
	<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	<i>P. syringae</i>	<i>P. avenae</i>	<i>P. glumae</i>
Lipase	+	-	-	-
Gelatin liquefaction	+	+	-	d
Arginine dihydrolase	+	-	-	-
Oxidase	+	-	+	-
Utilization of				
Sucrose	-	+	-	-
Inositol	-	+	-	+
Arginine	+	-	-	+
H ₂ S production	+	-	-	-
NO ₃ - reduction	-	-	+	+
Levan formation from sucrose	-	+	-	-
Growth at 37°C	+	-	+	+
41°C	-	-	+	+

^aReactions of 30 isolates of *P. avenae*, 11 isolates of *P. syringae*, 6 isolates of *P. glumae*, and 100 isolates of *P. fuscovaginae*. + = positive reaction, - = negative reaction, d = variable reaction.

the same results as *P. fuscovaginae* for the key characters. We also have recovered both *P. avenae* and *P. fuscovaginae* from a single discolored

grain sample. In cases where bacteria are suspected of causing GID, both fluorescent and nonfluorescent isolates should be tested for pathogenicity. □

Influences of rice straw, potash, and the fungicide benomyl on brown spot disease of rice

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Brown spot disease of rice caused by the fungus *Helminthosporium oryzae* and generally considered to be related to nutritional imbalances in Sierra Leone, is particularly serious in rainfed lowland rice affected by soil problems with inadequate water. In highly weathered, leached, and acid upland soils, the disease can be devastating to rice.

We studied the effect of amending upland rice soils with rice straw and potash and foliar application of benomyl on incidence of brown spot disease.

The trial was conducted at the station's upland site in Rokupr in northwest Sierra Leone, where soil cation exchange capacity ranges from 5 to 10 meq/100 g of soil and exchangeable cations are low. pH was 4.8. Annual rainfall averages 2,900 mm.

Effect of rice straw incorporation, potash application, and the fungicide benomyl on the incidence of brown spot disease of rice (variety ROK3). Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1983 wet season.

Treatment	Mean estimated leaf area affected (%)
Rice straw ash	5.73
Rice straw half mulch, half ash	6.20
Rice straw half mulch and half ash + benomyl + K	15.97
Rice straw mulch	6.42
Rice straw ash + K	6.53
K + benomyl	17.97
K	6.60
Rice straw mulch + K	6.48
Rice straw mulch +benomyl	17.70
Benomyl	18.62
Rice straw ash +benomyl	13.42
Control	7.48
LSD (0.05)	2.00
CV (%)	10.0

Rice straw was applied at 3 t/ha (mulched, ashed, or combined) 2 wk before seeding; muriate of potash was applied at 40 kg K₂O/ha in 3 equal splits 2, 6, and 10 wk after seeding; benomyl was sprayed at weekly intervals, starting 3 wk after seeding, for a total of 4 sprayings.

All treatments received 80-17.6 kg NP/ha, N as commercial urea was applied in 3 equal splits, P as single superphosphate basally.

Straw and potash ameliorated brown spot incidence somewhat, but the

differences were not significant (see table).

Benomyl significantly increased disease incidence, most severely in plots without potash and straw.

The indications are that the causal organism of brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae* is not only resistant to benomyl, but the compound enhances pathogen proliferation. □

Virulence of *Pyricularia oryzae* in coastal Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated the pathogenic variability of the blast (B1) pathogen in microplots in irrigated ricefields in Andhra Pradesh during 1986-87. Leaf B1 samples were collected from different ricefields, in West Godavari district, an endemic B1 region, during the dry season. The experiments were conducted in raised upland beds at DRR.

Virulence was evaluated on international B1 differentials and a few selected commercial varieties. Each cultivar was sown 10 cm apart, in 5 rows, each 50 cm long, with 2 replications. Seedlings were raised with 100 kg N/ha. Irrigation was provided by running overhead sprinklers for 2 h during the day and again toward evening. Night temperatures were favorable to B1 (20-24°C). There was no background infection prior to artificial inoculation.

Three experiments were conducted simultaneously (see table): 1) five monoconidial isolates (MI) obtained from different lesions were inoculated singly to a set of varieties; 2) a conidial population derived from 100 MI from a single lesion; and 3) 500 MI obtained from 20 lesions, 4 each from 5 villages, were inoculated to corresponding sets of varieties.

MI were multiplied by transferring single spores aseptically on sterilized sorghum seeds and incubating at room temperature (24-28 °C) for 10 d. Conidial suspensions (1×10^6 conidia/ml of water) of MI were made and mixed for each experiment. Test

Reaction^a of international B1 differentials and commercials to MI and mixture of populations of *P. oryzae*. Coastal Andhra Pradesh, 1986-87.

Cultivar	IRRI accession no.	Cultivar reaction to		
		Monoconidial isolates (MI)	Mixture of MI from one lesion	Mixture of MI from 20 lesions
<i>International B1 differential</i>				
Raminad Str. 3	32557	R	R	R
Zenith	32558	R	R	R
NP125	32559	S	S	S
Usen	32560	S	S	S
Dular	32561	R	R	R
Kanto 51	32562	S	S	S
Shia-tia-tsao (S)	32563	S	S	S
Caloro	32564	S	S	S
International race		IC-9	IC-9	IC-9
<i>Commercial varieties</i>				
Rasi		MR	MR	MR
IET2508		R	R	R
IET5656		R	R	R
IR50		S	S	S
IR36		MR	MR	MR
IR64		R	R	R

^a Based on the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice*, where scores 1-2 = necrotic spots (R), 3 = restricted sporulating lesions of 1-3 mm (MR), 4-9 = susceptible lesions of 1-3 cm or more (S).

seedlings were inoculated at 14 d by spraying spore suspension with a plastic sprayer in the evening. Inoculated nursery beds were covered with polythene sheets held on metallic frames from 1800 to 0800 h daily. B1 was scored

7 and 10 d after inoculation.

There was little variation in the populations of the pathogen. The reaction pattern exhibited in all three experiments was that of race IC-9. □

Differential culture medium for *Pseudomonas* species causing sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (GID) of rice

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The four *Pseudomonas* species (*P. avenae*, *P. fuscovaginae*, *P. glumae*, and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola*) that cause

GID in rice cannot be reliably distinguished from one another by symptom expression on diseased plants. Even *P. fuscovaginae* and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* that cause both ShR and GID, cannot be ruled out as causal agents of bacterial grain rot when sheath symptoms are absent. The geographical distributions of these species overlap considerably.

A rapid and relatively simple method to distinguish the species would be useful in developing varietal tolerance for bacterial GID, since lines showing